

LOSSES OF AGRICULTURAL LAND AND IMPACTS ON ENVIRONMENT: A STUDY ON RAJSHAHI DISTRICT OF BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

Bangladesh is a small country but it bears a huge population, resulting in a very high density of population and very high intensity of land and resource use. But it facing drastically experience of fast growing urbanization, population bombing and dramatically increases of food production. Two significantly prominent phenomena driving country's overall scenario of economic development and environment imbalance include: (a) the high growth rate of population engulfing precious land for settlement and (b) environmental degradation due to food production for ever increasing demand of food. As a result, the people using land more intensively and roughly for increase per unit food production. Every year the country is losing 1% arable land due to the population growth and its infrastructure development. This study was conducted at the Rajshahi district of Bangladesh during 1977-2010 where the major focus was to see the land use pattern of the area, losses of agricultural land and its impacts on environment. For analyses the loss of arable land remotely sensed data (Landsat MSS-1977, TM-1990 and TM2010) and GIS techniques were used and for impacts determination participatory rural appraisal method has been used and secondary data were collected from SPARRSO, published and unpublished data regarding crop, population and other ambient information from mostly government sources. Results show that the agricultural land of Rajshahi district loses, population increasing and for demand of population food production increases but to do it the environment degrading in many ways. If the proper land use and environment management programmed is not taken, the study area will faced significantly environmental hazard. The study was conducted at the Department of Geography, Environment and Urban Planning, Pabna University of Science and Technology, Pabna, Bangladesh.

Keywords: Agricultural Land, Losses, Impacts and Environment.

INTRODUCTION

Rajshahi district is one of the largest populated districts of Bangladesh but smallest one according to area. Rajshahi district is a traditionally educational and newly industrial arena and the rate of population growth is very high (1.34%) (BBS, 2008). This area is restricted so the basic requirements of the people have to maintain by the limited land area of the district. Hasty growth rate of population is responsible for rapid expansion of infrastructures. Fast growing rate of infrastructures causes of losses of agricultural land. Every year almost 0.47 percent of its arable land loses in this district (Islam and Hassan, 2011). The arable land decreasing day by day but population is increasing rapidly. Despite the remarkable achievement in controlling the high birth rate, the population continues to grow each year because of the large existing population base (Mahabub, IRRI). For change detection and find out the agricultural land losing rate remote sensing and Geographical information system (GIS) techniques has been used. Due to the losses of agricultural land and produced more food the arable land uses intensively in various way. This unplanned use of agricultural land creates worse impacts (i.e. pollution, ground water level decreasing, arsenic pollution, fertility losses, biodiversity losses and so on) on environment. In this regard, it is much need to control the agricultural land losing rate and keep district's environment livable. In this article, analysis is performed by remotely sensed data (LANDSAT TM-1977, LANDSAT MSS-1990 & LANDSAT MSS-2010) and some reliable sources (BBS, SRDI, BMDA and others government and non-government information desks) secondary data. For the impacts detection primary data have been collected by PRA Survey method and SPSS, MS Excel used for analysis the data. The result found that the agricultural land of the study area decreasing at a faster rate and environment degraded. This kind of analytic research can be remarkable in making land use plan and much livable environment.

The spatial extent of this study is between 2412 to 2412 N latitude and 8815 to 8850 E longitude which belongs to Rajshahi district of Bangladesh. Its covers an area of 2407 sq. km, is bounded by Naogaon District to the North, Natore district to the East, Chapai Nawabgong district to the West and the the river Padma to the South. Its commonly known as “Barriad Track”. It consist of 9 upazilas, 4 Thanas, 13 Municipalities, 147 Wards, 297 Mahallas, 70 union parishads, 1678 Mouzas and 1858 villiges (Banglapedia, 2005). Under Kopen climatic classification Rajshahi district has a topical wet and dry climate. The average temperature is 22⁰C-25⁰C and rainfall is about 1448 mm. Total land of the study area is 5994405 ha, where agricultures, Infrastructural and others constitute 394986.32 ha, 117615.42 ha and 63829.42 ha respectively. Total population o the study area is 2833256 and population density is 1177 per sq. km (BBS, 2008). Rajshahi district has been passing through a hasty process of urbanization and population growth since the last few decades. Rapid growth of population, unplanned urbanization, industrialization and agricultural modernization in the outer periphery area of this district city has created pressure on the agricultural land and as well as on environment. The area has been experiencing hasty changes in land use pattern especially the agricultural land decreasing rapidly and non agricultural land use suspiciously increasing. The district’s population will over around 1.2 million by 2030 when an extra 25 percent grains will have to be produced. But the additional harvests will have to be reaped from a much smaller area of cropland than is now available (Bhuiyan, 2003). To producing extra food from a less arable land the farmers uses more and more fertilizers, chemicals, underground water and so on. This uses are creates pressures; likes soil fertility decreasing, Environment degradation, underground water level decreasing, Arsenic contamination, biodiversity losses, increasing CFC (Cloro-floro carbon) imitations and so on. In a word agricultural land losses create an extra pressure on environment. The objective of this study was to detect the agricultural land losing rate and inspect the environmental problem.

MEHTODOLOGY

The study was conducted at the Department of Geography, Environment and Urban Planning, Pabna University of Science and Technology, Pabna, Bangladesh. Data were collected from Rajshahi district of Bangladesh during 1977 to 2010. Based on the availability of data in Bangladesh, the primary and secondary both type data used in this study. The primary data have been collected from “SPARSSO” and through PRA method and the secondary data have been collected from the most the government census data and non-government Published and unpublished data. The most important data for conducting this study is satellite image data (LANDSAT TM-1977, LANDST MSS-1990 & LANDSAT MSS 2010) have been collect from SPARRSO. For analyzing this image data GPS survey have been done and Arc GIS software used for preparing the land use map of the different time period and measured the area of different features of those map. This statistical data of the study area have been used for land use change detection and find out the agricultural land losses rate and for this used various statistical software. This study has selected some environmental issues as the variables which are most common scenery in the study area. This information’s are mostly collected by the field survey and analyzed by using various statistical techniques.

DISCUSSION

Land use pattern of the study area

The major land use pattern of Rajshahi district has been categorized into the following classes: agricultural land, infrastructural land, orchard, water bodies, fallow land, char land, char agricultural land, and river area. Total land area of Rajshahi district is 233794.44 hectare. Of this, agricultural land is 159711.06 hectare, infrastructural land 47415.14 hectare, orchard 4499.55 hectare, fallow land 4482.09 hectare, water bodies 8023.27 hectare, char land 5377.24 hectare and river area 3055.72 hectare acres. The land use pattern of the study area in 1977, 1990 and 2010 is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Pattern of land use.

Land use type	Area in 1977 (In hectare)	Area in 1990 (In hectare)	Area in 2010 (In hectare)
Agricultural	186056.74	177564.64	159913.48
Infrastructural	16161.30	26017.23	47617.57
Orchard	3781.95	3438.42	4499.55
Fallow land	8666.05	6613.66	4482.09
Water body	10235.95	10410.93	8428.13
Char land	2071.20	4393.17	5377.24
River	6429.12	4951.13	3055.72

(Source: LANDSAT MSS-1977, LANDSAT TM-1990 and LANDSAT TM-2010).

Losses of agricultural land

The land use changing pattern of Rajshahi district described above revealed that the agricultural land is facing a greater challenge. The agricultural land of Rajshahi district in 1977 was 186056.74 ha (*i.e.* 75.58% of the total land area) and in 2010 it became 159913.48 ha (68.31%) (Islam and Hassan, 2008). It has therefore been decreased to 14.02% during the last 33 years, indicating 0.46% decline per year. If this rate is constant and proper step would not be taken than the agricultural land of the study area will be drop out within next 217 years. In fig. 1 shows the agricultural land losses scenario.

Fig. 1. Losses of Agricultural Land of Rajshahi District from 1977-2010.

(Source: Satellite Images of 1977-MSS, 1990-TM, 2010-TM analysis).

Impacts of agricultural land losses on environment

The agricultural land of the study area has been gradually decreasing day by day but population of the study area increasing. In 1977 the total arable land area was 186056.74 ha and in 2010 its 159913.48 ha. But population of the study area was 7,46,000 only and in 2010 it becomes 28,33000. That means in previous 33 years the population of the study area increases almost 4 times. For this extra grown up people it very essential to meet their food demand, settlements and others basic need within the less arable land area than previous. Beside to meet up the food demand of this extra added population the farmer uses HYV, chemical fertilizer, pesticide, underground water, intensively cultivate and so on and its creates extra pressures on environment in various way. In table 2 and fig. 2 shows the arable land loss and population growth.

Table 2. Losses of arable land.

Year	Agricultural land (In hectare)	Differences from	% of decreasing	Rate of changes per year (%)
1977	185938.05	-	-	-
1990	177451.33	1977-1990	4.57	-0.36
2010	161391.41	1990-2010	11.03	-0.55
		1977-2010	14.05	-0.43

Source: Remote sensing survey, 2011.

Fig. 2. Population growth of study area.

Land fertility decreases

The arable land is decreasing day by day but population increasing at a fast growth rate. For these the farmer try to increased the production per unit and to pursuit it they uses more and more chemical fertilizer, salt, pesticides, and others things that's destructive for land fertility. The excessive and improper land use caused land degradation. The land degradation situation is going to severe in near future (Alam, 2006). Introduction of modern varieties increases the yield potential dramatically, but requires higher input levels under this technology, optimal fertilizer, irrigation and pesticide use (Pagiola, 1995). Moreover due to the intensive cultivating the biomass of the land can't be stored. In the study area the farmer sometimes uses annually 90 kg Nitrogen fertilizer per bigha in a triple crops land. In fig. 3 and fig. 4 shows the account of land fertility decreases and uses of chemical fertilizer.

Fig. 3. Losses of fertility.

Fig. 4. Fertilizers uses increasing.

Environment pollution

Environment polluted means the component of environment such as air, water, odor, soil etc are polluted due to the decreasing the arable land. The farmer uses pesticide, chemical fertilizer, salt and other toxic in all types of crops. In the life cycle of a crops 3 to 150 times they use chemical fertilizer and pesticide in the study area. Fig. 5 shows the use of pesticide in some selected crops. This chemical fertilizer polluted the soil, air and water. The pesticide that the farmer sprays in their crops this polluted

Fig. 5. Use of pesticide in study area.

the air and water flow as well as odor. Use of agro-chemicals can also result in health problems through pollution of drinking water by residues. Here the effects of fertilizer use are also a concern. Nitrates can be carcinogenic, for example and can lead to blue baby syndrome (Pagiola, 1995). Just 20 years before the farmers are not uses any type of pesticide and fertilizer. It's very alarming that almost 100 types of insecticides are available in market and farmers use them without proper knowledge. Fig. 6 shows the use of pesticide.

Underground water level depletion

Rajshahi district is a part of Barind Tract that's naturally dry region of Bangladesh. The water stored in the ground can be compared to money kept in a bank account. If withdraw money at a faster rate than deposit new money will eventually start having account-supply problems. With the increasing use of ground water for agricultural, municipal, industrial needs, the annual extraction of groundwater are far in excess of net average recharge from natural sources (Asaduzzaman *et al.*, 2012). Pumping water out of the ground faster than it is replenished over the long-term cause's similar problems. The volume of groundwater in storage is decreasing in many areas of the Rajshahi district in response to pumping. Due to the climate change the seasonal rainfall decrease and the farmer are fully depended on underground water for irrigation. For this cause the numbers of deep tub-well increase day by day. After the introduction of BMDP in 1986, there are about 6,000 deep tube-well sare installed in the area. In addition to that about 66,000 shallow tube-wells are available in this area and due to the water level decreasing drying up of wells, reduction of water in streams and lakes, deterioration of water quality, increased pumping costs, land subsidence. During the summer season the water level decreasing too much and then the hand tub-well become unable to get water that's creates pure drinking water scarcity in this reason. Villagers in Barind Tract area in Godagari upazila are always after water as the underground water table is going down by 1 to 2 feet every year (Daily Star, 2010). In fig. 6 shows the ground water level depletion in this region.

Fig. 6. Ground water level depletion in study area.

Arsenic contamination

Due to the underground water level decreasing the arsenic contamination is increasing in this region. The contamination of groundwater by arsenic in Bangladesh is the largest poisoning of a population in history, with millions of people exposed (Smith *et al.*, 2000). There are a complementary relationship between ground water level depletion and arsenic contamination. The health effects of ingesting arsenic contaminated drinking water appear slowly. For this reason, a more important issue than the number of patients who currently have arsenic caused diseases in the exposure to arsenic. In the study area 85% of the respondents heard about arsenic and 88% have their own tube-well or water's motor. Almost 27% of tube-wells contaminated by arsenic in the Rajshahi district. In study area almost 12% of people suffered by arsenic caused disease in their life time.

Health impacts

FAO analysis of pesticide composition revealed high shares of toxic chemicals (for example, carbamates and organophosphates in insecticides and dithiocarbamates and inorganics in fungicides)

which have been known to cause cancer, genetic damage, fetal damage and severe allergic responses in exposed populations (Zahm *et al.*, 1997). Many pesticides used in Rajshahi district are also banned or restricted under international agreements (Meisner, 2004; NOVIB, 1993; SOS-arsenic.net, 2004, SUNS, 1998). Pesticide suppliers in Rajshahi district even continue to sell the 12 particularly controversial pesticides known by activists campaigning worldwide as the “dirty dozen” (SUNS, 1998; SOS-arsenic.net, 2004). In addition, substantial anecdotal evidence suggests that users’ lack of information have led to widespread overuse or misuse of pesticides. As a result, pesticide poisonings and ecological damage have become common in Bangladesh (Ramaswamy, 1992). In study area most of the farmers have not knowledge about pesticide and its using guidelines, effectiveness, degree of uses, frequency and intervals of uses. In fig. 7 shown that the uses of pesticide at some selected crops.

Fig. 7. Health impact of pesticide in the study area.

Biodiversity losses

Bio diversity lose is another adverse impacts of agricultural land loss. Rajshahi district enrich with biodiversity , the local people investigation, 81 plant taxa belonged to 71 genera under 43 families were mentioned by them having economic importance, of which only the medico-botanical values of them were highlighted. Out of these plants species, 31% belonged to herbs, 29 trees, 11 shrubs and 10 climbers (Rahman, 2013). But its frightening that already some local biological species extinct and some of them are in survive somehow. Agricultural land is losing and the farmer production demand increases, for these they are cultivating high yielding varieties and uses chemical fertilizer and pesticide. As a result of HYV cultivation traditional species are losing day by day. Moreover due to unrest land cultivation and excess use of pesticide a huge number of environment friendly pests cannot survive. In figure shows biodiversity losses picture of the study area.

Fig. 8. Losses of bio-diversity in the study area.

CONCLUSION

Agricultural land of the study area losing and the farmers produce more food gain in less arable land. For this these creates extra pressure on agricultural land as well as on environment. Agricultural land related problems could appear in vast manner in future all over the country. Now it’s very essential to practice sustainable agricultural land management. The chemical fertilizers and insecticides are being used in agricultural land. Whenever we need to reduce the using of chemical fertilizers and insecticides in agricultural land then we are using these harmful things in land to increase food production. So we

should reduce it and should make policies to reduce. The farmer should cultivated green plants that's root and leaves rebuild the soil fertility. The agricultural land is being cultivated with the help of irrigation. Underground water is the only source for Irrigation. As a result the level of underground water is decreasing due to the excessive use. The iron, Arsenic mixed with underground water causes damage to the cultivable land, when it is used excessively. To dig canals, ponds, rivers, lakes are necessary as a solution to this problem. The using of agricultural land in non-agricultural use affects agricultural land. The buildings, houses, offices, banks, factories, industries affect the nearby agricultural land by leaving wastes on agricultural land and creating problem in irrigation and ploughing. So the using of agricultural land in non agricultural use should be stopped. So, its right time to take decision about the sustainable agricultural land management policy otherwise the study area faced environmental vulnerability in near future.

REFERENCES

- Alam, M. S. 2006. Restoration and protection of agricultural land in Bangladesh. www.alchemicalnursery.org/index2.php?option=com...task...
- Asaduzzaman, M., S. Kar and A. Asad. 2012. Environmental impact due to groundwater level depletion. *Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA)* ISSN: 2248-9622 www.ijera.com Vol. 2, Issue 6, November-December 2012, pp.1465-1467.
- Banglapedia, 2006. *National Encyclopedia of Bangladesh*. Asiatic Society of Bangladesh. Genesis Printing and Packaging, Dhaka.
- BBS, 2008. Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, Economic Review 2008. Ministry of Planning. Government of Bangladesh.
- Bhuiyan, M. 2003. *Has urbanization caused agricultural land loss?* The Daily Star, November 1, 2003.
- Islam, R. and Z. Hassan. 2011. Land use changing pattern and challenges for agricultural land: A study on Rajshahi district, *Journal of Life and Earth Science, Rajshahi University*, pp. 69-74.
- Meisner, 2004. NOVIB, 1993; SOS-arsenic.net, 2004
- Pagiola, S. 1995. Environmental and natural resource degradation in intensive agriculture in Bangladesh. *Environment development paper, paper no. 15. Environmental Sustainable development, World Bank*.
- Rahman, A. H. M. M. 2013. Medico-botanical study of the plants found in the Rajshahi district of Bangladesh. *Prudence Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* Vol. 1(1), pp. 1-8.
- Ramaswamy, S. 1992. Pest Control and Environment. *Notes for discussion at a seminar on environment and agriculture*. Agriculturalist Association of Bangladesh, Dhaka, p.19.
- Smith, A. H, Lingas EO and Rahman A. 2004. Contamination of drinking-water by arsenic SOS Arsenic.net 2004. *Agrochemicals: Imported Pollutants in Bangladesh*. Available at: <http://www.sos-arsenic.net/index.html>.
- SUNS, 1998. Pesticide Overuse Takes Serious Turn in Bangladesh. *Monday, Jan. 24, (Dhaka, Jan. 23 IPS/Tabibul Islam)*.
- WHO, 2000. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. Bangladesh: a public health emergency. Ref. No. 00-0751. 2000, 78 (9) # 1093 <http://www.prudencejournals.org/pjmpr/index.htm>
- Zahm, S. H., M. H. Ward and A. Blair. 1997. Pesticides and Cancer. In: *Occupational Medicine: State of the Art Reviews*. Vol. 12: Pesticides (M. Keifer, ed.). Philadelphia: Hanley and Belfus, Inc., 269-289.